

SYNTHESIS OF MIXED-LIGAND COORDINATION COMPOUNDS OF COBALT(II) ION AND KETOROLAC

Karimova Momojon Egamberganovna

PhD student the Khorezm Ma'mun Academy

Khudoyberganov Aybek Ikromovich

PhD., Senior Scientific Researcher, Khorezm Ma'mun Academy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17174080>

Abstract. This article presents the results of research on the synthesis and analysis of mixed-ligand coordination compounds of cobalt (II) ion with ketorolac and amides. Solvent-based methods were selected for the synthesis process, in which cobalt (II) salts (such as chloride or acetate), ketorolac, and various amides (formamide, acetamide, nicotinamide) reacted in specific molar ratios to form new coordination compounds. To determine the structure and composition of the complexes, IR, UV-Vis, and NMR spectral analyses, as well as elemental analysis and X-ray diffraction (XRD), were employed. Thermal analysis was used to establish the thermal stability of the complexes. During the study, the coordination interactions of ligands with cobalt (II) ions, their electronic configuration, and biological activity were examined, and corresponding conclusions were drawn.

Keywords: Ketorolac, formamide, acetamide, nicotinamide, coordination compound, synthesis, analysis, coordination capacity, thermal stability, solubility, reaction yield.

One of the most relevant areas of modern coordination chemistry and bioinorganic chemistry is the synthesis of new coordination compounds based on biologically active ligands and the study of their properties. In particular, complexes of transition metals such as cobalt attract special interest due to their wide range of biological activities, including antibacterial, antifungal, and antitumor properties [1,2]. The cobalt (II) ion, owing to its electronic configuration and wide coordination numbers, can form stable coordination compounds with a variety of ligands; their structural features and bioactivity largely depend on the nature of the ligands [3]. Ketorolac is a systemically active non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), whose pharmacological effect is mainly achieved through the inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis. However, at high doses, it carries the risk of damaging the gastrointestinal mucosa [4]. In modern pharmaceutical chemistry, the synthesis of metal complexes of drugs is considered a promising approach to enhance drug efficacy and reduce side effects. It is well established that when organic ligands form complexes with

metal ions, their biological activity can significantly increase, often associated with improved metabolic stability and enhanced solubility in water [5].

I. First, the required reagents and apparatus were collected, including $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_3$ (ketorolac), amides (formamide, acetamide, nicotinamide), ethanol, NaOH, distilled water, and laboratory glassware. The synthesis of the complex compound with the composition $\text{Co}(\text{ket})_2(\text{HCONH}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ was carried out as follows.

A solution of 0.745 g (2.0 mmol) ketorolac tromethamine in 20 mL of hot methanol was prepared and transferred into a burette. In the next step, 0.238 g (1.0 mmol) of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in 10 mL of a methanol–water mixture. Separately, a solution of formamide (HCONH_2 , 0.090 g, 2.0 mmol) was prepared. The cobalt salt solution was slowly added, with constant stirring, into the ketorolac solution over 15–20 minutes. The resulting green solution was then treated with the third component, formamide, which was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was heated at 50–60 °C (without boiling) for 2–3 hours using a magnetic stirrer. The mixture was subsequently cooled to room temperature, which improved the crystallization of the complex.

The pH of the reaction mixture was checked using pH paper or a pH meter. To adjust the pH to 6.5–7.0, 2–3 drops of triethylamine were added. This step was important to deprotonate the carboxylic acid group and prevent unnecessary protonation of formamide. A light green fine crystalline precipitate formed, which was filtered under vacuum through a Büchner funnel, washed with ethanol, and dried. The precipitate was also washed several times with cold methanol, and the absence of chloride ions in the coordination compound was confirmed by testing with 0.1 M AgNO_3 solution. The mass of the synthesized complex compound was measured, and the reaction yield was calculated. The yield (η) was found to be 67% [6].

Reaction equation:

II. The coordination compound $\text{Co}(\text{ket})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{CONH}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ was also synthesized by the above-mentioned method, and the reaction equation can be expressed as follows.

Reaction equation:

The yield (η) was found to be 68%.

III. The coordination compound $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ was also synthesized by the above-mentioned method, and the reaction equation can be expressed as follows.

The yield (η) was found to be 72%.

“Nicotinamide (nia) > Acetamide (acm) > Formamide (fm)”. In this sequence, the activity of the amides decreases. Nicotinamide is the strongest amide in the series, and the complex formed with it is the most stable and was obtained with the highest yield. All the synthesized complexes were obtained in colored forms: the nicotinamide complex appeared as blue-violet precipitates, the acetamide complex as brown precipitates, and the formamide complex as light-green precipitates. The composition of the synthesized coordination compounds was determined by elemental analysis, and the following results were obtained [7]. The metal content in the synthesized complexes was determined using a novAA 300 atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Analytik Jena AG, Germany) [8], while the elemental composition was analyzed with a EuroEA3000 CHNS-O Analyzer (Eurovector S.p.A., Milan, Italy) [9].

Table 1

Elemental analysis results of cobalt-ketorolac-amide coordination compounds

No	Coordination compound formula	Molecular formula:	Chemical elements	Theoretical %	Experimental %
1	$[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8\text{Co}$ M=603.53 g/mol	C	59,7	59,35
			H	4,69	4,82
			N	4,64	4,51
			O	21,20	-
2	$[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{HCONH}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ yoki $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{fm})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	$\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_4\text{O}_{10}\text{Co}$ o M=693.63 g/mol	C	55,41	55,12
			H	4,95	5,11
			N	8,08	7,89
			O	23,06	-
3	$[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{CONH}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ yoki $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{acm})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_4\text{O}_{10}\text{Co}$ o M=721.69 g/mol	C	56,58	56,20
			H	5,32	5,45
			N	7,77	7,62
			O	22,17	-
			Co	8,17	8,01

4	$[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ yoki $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{nia})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	$\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{42}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{10}\text{C}$ o M=849.83 g/mol	C	59,36	58,95
			H	4,99	5,18
			N	9,89	9,65
			O	18,87	-
			Co	6,93	6,75

Conclusion. New mixed-ligand complexes – $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{fm})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{acm})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, and $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{nia})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ – were successfully synthesized in a reproducible manner using ketorolac tromethamine, the corresponding cobalt(II) salt, and various amides in an aqueous-methanol medium. Shifts observed in the IR spectra confirmed that ketorolac coordinates to the cobalt(II) ion via its carboxylate group in a bidentate mode, while the amides act as monodentate ligands through either oxygen (fm, acm) or nitrogen (nia) donor atoms.

All synthesized cobalt(II) complexes exhibited higher antibacterial activity compared to the free ligands (ketorolac and amides) and even the simple $[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ complex. This clearly demonstrates the significant role of complex formation in enhancing antibiotic activity. Among the mixed-ligand complexes, antibacterial efficacy was found to depend on the nature and coordinating ability of the amide ligand, following the trend:

$[\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{nia})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] > [\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{acm})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] > [\text{Co}(\text{Ket})_2(\text{fm})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$
> ketorolac

References:

1. Abdel-Rahman L.H., et al. (2013). European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry, 64, 594–600.
2. Sadeek S.A., et al. (2019). Journal of Molecular Structure, 1175, 101-110.
3. Raman N., et al. (2012). Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy, 92, 175–183.
4. Gunturu S.K., et al. (2013). Journal of Pharmacology & Pharmacotherapeutics, 4(3), 230–231.
5. Jozsef S., et al. (2020). Coordination Chemistry Reviews, 420, 213-230.
6. Al-Amiery, A. A., Al-Majedy, Y. K., & Al-Najar, H. A. (2011). Synthesis, characterization and antibacterial activities of novel ketorolac metal complexes. Journal of the Chilean Chemical Society, 56(2), 639-641.
7. Fadeeva V. P., Tikhova V. D., and Nikulicheva O. N. Elemental Analysis of Organic Compounds with the Use of Automated CHNS Analyzers // Journal of Analytical Chemistry, 2008, -V.63(11), -P.1094–1106.

8. Charlot G. Methods of analytical chemistry. Quantitative analysis of inorganic compounds. -M.: Publishing house "Chemistry". 1965. –P. 975.
9. Bazhenova L.N. Quantitative elemental analysis of organic compounds. - Yekaterinburg: 2008. – P. 356.

